

Calculations of the principal neutronic characteristics of a hypothetical VVER assembly with minor actinides incorporated into $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ fuel in a duplex configuration

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Abstract

The VVER-1200/AES-2006 is recognized as a leading Gen III+ nuclear reactor design, meeting stringent international safety standards. This study evaluates the use of a novel $\text{PuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ duplex fuel, incorporating weapon-grade plutonium (WgPu) and thorium, for a hypothetical VVER-1200 assembly. The research also explores incorporating minor actinides (MAs) for transmutation, comparing two methods: MAs coated on WgPuO_2 and MAs mixed with WgPuO_2 as integral fuel burnable absorber rods. Neutronic properties of these fuels are compared to those of LEU-fueled assemblies. The results show a 135% higher burnup for the duplex fuel compared to LEU, with extended criticality, reduced reactivity swings, and lower Pu-239 concentrations upon discharge. While Np-237 and Am-241 concentrations decrease, Am-243, Cm-244, and Cm-245 increase, but overall radiotoxic waste is reduced. Enhanced safety coefficients are also observed, within acceptable LWR ranges.

Keywords

VVER-1200 assembly, Duplex Fuel, Plutonium, Thorium, Minor Actinides

Introduction

Recently, there has been an increase in global demand for energy to achieve social and environmental justice for the world's growing and developing inhabitants. Nuclear energy appears to be an appealing option due to its low carbon footprint; however, it has faced many challenges since its inception, manifested in a lack of trust from the public, anti-nuclear, and political classes for a variety of reasons, most notably the operational safety and nuclear wastes in

spent fuel. To reestablish this lost trust, nuclear reactors planned for construction or nuclear fuels proposed for use must overcome the aforementioned obstacles.

The use of conventional nuclear reactors, for example, generates large amounts of irradiated fuel (i.e. spent fuel). A conventional light water reactor (LWR) with a capacity of 1 GWe that uses low-enriched uranium oxide (LEU UO_2) will typically discharge 20 to 25 tonnes of irradiated fuel per year of operation. Irradiated UO_2 fuel is composed mainly of uranium, predominantly U-238,

with a small fraction of unburned U-235, which typically accounts for about 4 to 5 wt.% of the spent fuel. Additionally, it contains approximately 1 wt. % of plutonium and around 0.1 to 0.2 wt.% of MAs, along with about 4 to 5 wt.% of other fission products (OECD/NEA 2013). Given the above, large amounts of plutonium have accumulated in the world in the form of burned fuel. According to IAEA reports, the ongoing global spread of discharged plutonium poses a significant proliferation risk (IAEA 1998; Kotlyar et al. 2017). Furthermore, fuel with a low burnup, typically around 1 GWd/ton, has been shown to yield weapons-grade plutonium (World Nuclear Association 2017; Abdelghafar Galahom 2020). Because of growing public and political concern about the potential misuse of this plutonium, the need to address this surplus has gained prominence. Therefore, an appealing and viable approach for reducing plutonium inventories is the reutilization of this material as reactor fuel. This strategy not only helps mitigate the proliferation risk but also offers a practical solution for managing surplus plutonium.

Long-lived byproducts, commonly referred to as MAs, are produced through activation and fission during reactor operation and tend to accumulate in spent fuel. The most commonly abundant MAs in this context typically consist of a triad of elements, namely neptunium (Np), americium (Am), and curium (Cm). As the used fuel is subjected to higher burnup levels, additional minor actinides such as berkelium (Bk) and californium (Cf) also become significant contributors to the mix. MAs pose a problem to nuclear environmental safety because they are responsible for a significant contribution to spent nuclear fuel radiotoxicity (OECD/NEA 2013) having major conse-

quences in radiation protection issues of waste treatment and disposal. To reduce the amount of actinides in spent fuel, it is best to recycle them alongside the plutonium in thermal and fast reactors. Np-237, Am-241, and Am-243 have very large thermal neutron capture cross-sections (Fig. 1), therefore, these MAs can capture thermal neutrons and transform into Pu-239, Am-242, Am-244, Cm-243, or Cm-245, which have thermal fission cross-sections between large and moderate, and thus may serve as alluring fissile materials (Liu et al. 2014; Galahom and Sharaf 2021). Furthermore, since MAs have very large thermal neutron capture cross-sections, they can act as burnable absorbers (BAs) when introduced into reactors to reduce the initial reactivity of fresh fuel (Benrhnia et al. 2022a). Consequently, the use of these MAs may be beneficial in reducing initial reactivity due to the presence of highly fissile Pu-239. The epithermal cross-sections of these MAs contain resonance regions, which are beneficial in the LWRs spectrum to increase the negative temperature coefficients, particularly the moderator temperature coefficient, because in the case of Pu-based fuels, as the temperature of the moderator increases, the Maxwellian region of the neutron spectrum shifts slightly towards higher neutron energies, potentially benefiting the fission resonance of Pu-239 and Pu-241 (Richards and Serfontein 2014; Kabach et al. 2021; Zou et al. 2021). What's more, one of the distinct benefits of recycling MAs and using them as a BAs option is that it may be a way to reduce the concentration of boric acid in the moderator. Therefore, all of these characteristics can significantly reduce the possibility of a criticality accident in a fuel cycle (Liu et al. 2014).

Figure 1. Capture cross-sections of MAs (Zou et al. 2021) (a); Th-232 and U-238 (b); and Pu-238, Pu-240, and Pu-242 (c).

According to the available literature, many studies have been conducted to investigate the recycling of plutonium and MAs separately or together in thermal or fast reactors. However, it appears that the vast majority of studies conducted by researchers in LWRs are focused on the recycling of plutonium in uranium-based mixed-oxides (Emmett and Ans 2000; NEA 2002; Gomin et al. 2006) or thorium-based fuels (Galahom 2018; Galahom 2020). The majority of studies on MAs suggest recycling in LEU-fueled reactors (Taiwo et al. 2006; OECD/NEA 2013; Liu et al. 2014), and no research study has focused on using both plutonium and MAs in thorium-based fuel. Burning plutonium and MAs in LEU-fueled LWRs is ineffective because the fertile U-238 is the main source of the residual high quantities of plutonium and other long-lived radioactive actinides. On the other hand, replacing U-238 with Th-232 will result in not only more new fissile material (U-233) but also lower waste inventories. U-233, like Pu-239 and Pu-241, is a fissile isotope with a long half-life that can be produced in reactors via single-neutron capture. It has a fast critical mass that is nearly identical to Pu-239, but the spontaneous fission rate is much lower, reducing the problem of a spontaneous fission neutron prematurely initiating the chain reaction to negligible levels (Kang and von Hippel 2001). Another advantage is that, unlike U-233, the plutonium produced from standard UO_2 fuels is a wasting asset due to the fissile Pu-241's short half-life, which decays to non-fissile Am-241 (Galahom 2018).

Another significant advantage of incorporating Th-232 is its notable sensitivity to resonance cross-sections concerning temperature under self-shielded conditions, known as the thorium Doppler effect. Although the effective resonance integral for a given temperature is greater for U-238 when compared to Th-232, the change in this integral per degree is more pronounced for Th-232. Consequently, reactors utilizing Th-232 will exhibit more substantial negative feedback on neutron multiplication with increasing fuel temperature (Doppler coefficient) than those using U-238 (Belle and Berman 1984; Kabach 2021; Kabach et al. 2021a, 2021b). This characteristic results in an enhanced negative Doppler coefficient. Consequently, it is proposed that WgPu and MAs be recycled in thorium-based reactors to breed additional nuclear fuel and provide a solution for nuclear waste management.

There are three main approaches to utilizing thorium in LWRs: homogeneous, macro-heterogeneous, and micro-heterogeneous. The homogeneous method, which mixes thorium with fissile material (e.g., plutonium in this case), is the simplest. The resulting fuel is called mixed oxide fuel (Abdelghafar Galahom and Ibrahim 2022; Abdelghafar Galahom et al. 2024). However, this method increases fuel costs over the cycle. It also requires the fabrication of mixed oxide fuel, and the fuel exhibits suboptimal neutronic performance due to the higher fissile loading needed, compared to LEU, to maintain the standard cycle length in PWRs (Li et al. 2021; Benrhnia et al. 2022).

If thorium is separated from the fissile fuel, i.e., fissile fuel in the seed region of a fuel core or assembly, and thorium in the blanket region, the approach is known as macro-heterogeneous (i.e. seed-blanket) (Bromley 2016; El Banni et al. 2024). The concept of a macro-heterogeneous scheme can effectively use neutrons for breeding; however, this concept causes power imbalance and increases the temperature of the seed region at the beginning of cycle (BOC) (Li et al. 2021). The micro-heterogeneous approach has three main design types. The first method involves alternately stacking fissile and thorium pellets within a fuel rod in the axial direction. The second is a fuel assembly with fissile and thorium fuel rods arranged in a checkerboard pattern. The final type, known as duplex pellets, contains thorium and fissile zones radially with different volume ratios. According to relevant studies, the burnup of the MIT-proposed duplex fuel design can achieve a longer discharge life with a single batch for once-through fuel management (Joo et al. 2004; Rabir et al. 2020; El Kheiri et al. 2023a, 2023b).

The current work was undertaken with the primary objective of assessing the effectiveness of $\text{WgPuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ duplex fuel with MAs in an assembly-level analysis. The first objective of this research is to compare the fuel cycle performance of $\text{WgPuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ duplex fuel in the hexagonal assembly of the VVER-1200 reactor to that of a conventional LEU assembly. The next important objective of this research is to investigate the effects of adding MAs as the form of integral fuel burnable absorbers (IFBAs) located symmetrically within the fuel assembly on the $\text{WgPuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ duplex case, to investigate their effect on the fuel cycle, neutronic performance, and nuclear fuel depletion behavior. Because IFBA may contain neutron-absorbing materials that can be homogeneously mixed with fuel rod components or coated with the fuel rod, both options were explored in this research. Furthermore, the characteristics of the VVER-1200 assembly have been investigated using various types of loading designs and different loading thicknesses with their equivalent concentrations.

Material, model description, and input data

Assembly under consideration

A typical VVER-1200 reactor has 163 fuel assemblies (Galahom 2020). The assemblies are similar in size and are arranged in a hexagonal array. The hypothetical assembly model used in this paper is based on currently available information of a classic VVER-1200, and all essential information is provided in Tables 1–3. In general, each assembly has 312 fuel rod positions, 18 control rod guide tubes, and one central hole for an instrumentation tube. Each fuel rod can contain a maximum enrichment of 4.95 wt.% LEU fuel (U-235) (El Banni et al. 2022). The rods confined inside each fuel pin include an inner central void, which serves to provide additional volume for

gaseous fission products produced during fuel burnup, to reduce the maximum temperature in the fuel center, and to reduce stresses and, as a result, pellet cracking (Fejt et al. 2019). A similar gap exists between the outer side of the fuel pellet and the inner side of the cladding. Fig. 2 depicts a geometrical representation of one-sixth of the assembly model (2D) used for DRAGON calculations.

Figure 2. Geometric representation of one-sixth of the assembly model used for calculations.

Table 1. Geometrical specification of the reference VVER-1200 assembly considered in this study (El Banni et al. 2022)

Parameters	Value
Central void in the fuel pellet radius	0.060 cm
Outer fuel rod radius (UO ₂)	0.380 cm
Inner cladding radius	0.386 cm
Outer cladding radius	0.455 cm
Inner tube radius	0.545 cm
Outer tube radius	0.630 cm
Inner tube radius	0.550 cm
Outer tube radius	0.650 cm
Fuel rod pitch	1.275 cm
Fuel assembly pitch	23.6 cm

Table 2. Non-fuel material specification

Central Void	Material	Air
	Density	0.0003922 g/cm ³
Gap	Material	He
	Density	0.001598 g/cm ³
Cladding	Material	E110 (Nb 1 wt.%, O 0.060 wt.%, Zr 98.931 wt.%)
	Density	6.55 g/cm ³

Table 3. Estimated operational parameters for the VVER-1200 fuel assembly models

Fuel temperature	1100 K
Guide/Central tube temperature	600 K
Moderator temperature	573 K (density 0.7222 g/cm ³)
Boron concentration	0 ppm to 400 ppm

Simulation software

As aforementioned, the neutronic calculations were performed using the DRAGON -V5 code (Marleau et al. 2021) and the Draglib formatted open-source multi-group cross-section library ENDF/B-VIII.0 XMAS (172)

(Hébert 2008). DRAGON is a lattice cell code developed by École Polytechnique de Montréal that can solve the transport equation using the collision probability method, interface current method, or characteristics method. The code is organized as a modular structure, with the modules linked by the GAN generalized driver. Because the investigated assemblies have hexagonal geometries, geometrical modeling was performed in this work by the GEO module using an option compounded by three keywords: HBC, SA60, and REFL (HBC SA60 REFL), which defines a hexagonal symmetry of one-sixth of an assembly with reflective boundary conditions associated with the outer surfaces (Fig. 2). The EXCELT module was used to track full-cell collision probability using the isotropic surface current. The FLU module was used to solve the linear system of multigroup collision probability. The self-shielding calculations were carried out using the SHI module, which is based on the generalized Stammler method with the Livolant and Jeanpierre (LJ) option, and WIMS transport correction was applied to the cross-sections. The EDI module was used to provide the primary editing options to DRAGON. The EVO module was used to calculate depletion (Bouassa et al. 2023, 2024; Lkouz et al. 2023; Kabach et al. 2024). In this study. Simulations of depletion characteristics were carried out at the temperatures specified in Table 3, with a constant power density of 40 KW/kg used in all cases. Finally, the PSP module was used to generate a few PostScript images for the 2D geometry of the fuel rods.

Duplex fuel design

Different types of fuels, such as uranium-based fuels (e.g. UO₂, MOX, UC, and UN...) (Carbajo 2005; Mohsen et al. 2021) and thorium-based fuels (e.g. UO₂-ThO₂ and PuO₂-ThO₂,...) (Dwiddar et al. 2015; Galahom 2018), have been considered or investigated in the VVER-1000/1200 assemblies. Agreeing with the scope of this study, the latter options have primarily been investigated as homogeneously mixed or macro-heterogeneous seed-blanket arrangements. This study, on the other hand, focuses on the use of micro-heterogeneous Wg-PuO₂-ThO₂ duplex as potential fuel for future applications in order to burn the extra Pu-239 in WgPuO₂ while taking advantage of the benefits provided by thorium in the duplex configuration. The duplex WgPuO₂-ThO₂ fuel design analyzed in this work consists of WgPuO₂ in the inner region surrounded by an annulus of ThO₂ (Fig. 3). The WgPu composition by weight percentage is shown in Table 4. According to sensitivity and burnup studies performed in comparison with 4.95 wt.% (U-235) in the case of all-LEU, when WgPuO₂ occupies around 10% of the duplex configuration, it achieves the best performance in terms of initial reactivity, reactivity swing, and discharge burnup (135% greater than the LEU case). Results and discussion section will include an in-depth comparison. Table 5 shows the geometrical input for the LEU and WgPuO₂-ThO₂ cases.

Figure 3. Cross-sectional view of fuel pins designed with DRAGON code.

Table 4. Plutonium isotopic compositions used in the simulations (Radkowsky and Galperin 1998)

Isotope	Pu-238	Pu-239	Pu-240	Pu-241	Pu-242
Wt. %	0.02	93.80	5.80	0.35	0.03

Table 5. Geometrical input for the LEU and WgPuO₂-ThO₂ duplex cases

Category	Parameters	Value
Conventional fuel pin	Inner fuel rod radius	0.060 cm
	Outer fuel rod radius (LEU)	0.380 cm
Micro-heterogeneous duplex fuel pin	Outer seed fuel rod radius (WgPuO ₂)	0.133 cm
	Outer blanket fuel rod radius (ThO ₂)	0.380 cm

MAs incorporation design

A VVER reactor’s core is entirely made up of fuel assemblies, with no designated positions for MAs. Nonetheless, the assembly contains 331 positions (for fuel rods, control rods, and an instrumentation tube), which opens up a wide range of possibilities for MA transmutation and recycling. As previously stated, MAs have higher thermal capture cross-sections and thus can be classified as BAs; therefore, this study suggests using them as BAs, which may be advantageous when incorporating initial quantities of fissile Pu-239.

Of many types of BA configurations, these two types are mainly used in LWRs: integral fuel burnable absorbers (IFBAs) and burnable poison rods (BPRs), which occupy the control rod positions. IFBAs, on the other hand, are integrated with the fuel assembly, and these rods are positioned in optimally symmetrical locations to maximize benefits. According to the literature, there are several drawbacks when a BA is homogeneous with fuel, most

notably: the decomposition effects of the irradiated BA add to those of the fuel, which exacerbates fuel swelling and the buildup of fission gas pressure; and the addition of a BA to the fuel generally degrades the mechanical properties of the fuel or alloys, especially under irradiation. Discrete placement of the BAs, such as a fuel rod coated with a BA can mitigate these disadvantages when compared to a homogeneous mixture of fuel and BAs (Washington 2016).

In the context of the IFBA configuration, the absorber can either be mixed with or coated onto the fuel. The choice between homogeneous and heterogeneous recycling of MAs plays an essential role in the impact on fuel design. In this study, we have implemented both options, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Furthermore, we thoroughly investigate the effects of employing MAs as BAs in various designs and thicknesses, comparing them with their equivalent fraction in mixed cases. Our primary aim is to scrutinize their influence on the initial reactivity of the WgPuO₂-ThO₂ duplex case, fuel cycle dynamics, depletion patterns, the evolution of isotopic concentrations among the primary actinides under examination, and safety factors. For clarity, the compositions of MAs, including neptunium, americium, and curium, obtained from LWR spent fuel, are presented in Table 6 (Liu et al. 2014). Fig. 5 depicts cross-sectional views of the various investigated VVER assembly models with WgPuO₂-ThO₂ and MAs. Table 7 identifies the various assembly models.

Table 6. Minor actinide isotopic compositions used in the simulations (Liu et al. 2014)

Isotope	Np-237	Am-241	Am-243	Cm-244	Cm-245
Wt. %	56.20	26.40	12.00	5.12	0.28

Figure 4. Cross-sectional view of duplex fuel with MAs incorporation designs.

Figure 5. Cross-sectional view of VVER assembly with the studied IFBAs loading designs.

Table 7. Cases considered for the neutronic study of the VVER-1200 assembly

Case Name	Description
LEU_Ref	312 Fuel rods [nominal UO_2 fuel with 4.95 wt.% (U-235)]
Du_Ref	312 Fuel rods [duplex fuel: $\text{WgPuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$]
Du_12IFBAC-1 to 4	Du_Ref case with 12 IFBA MAs coated on the outer surface of WgPuO_2 (1) 0.003 cm, (2) 0.005 cm, (3) 0.008 cm, and (4) 0.011 cm.
Du_18IFBAC-1 to 4	Du_Ref case with 18 IFBA MAs coated on the outer surface of WgPuO_2 (1) 0.003 cm, (2) 0.005 cm, (3) 0.008 cm, and (4) 0.011 cm.
Du_30IFBAC-1 to 4	Du_Ref case with 30 IFBA MAs coated on the outer surface of WgPuO_2 (1) 0.003 cm, (2) 0.005 cm, (3) 0.008 cm, and (4) 0.011 cm.
Du_12IFBAM-1 to 4	Du_Ref case with 12 IFBA MAs mixed with WgPuO_2 (1) 5 wt.%, (2) 10 wt.%, (3) 15 wt.%, and (4) 20 wt.%.
Du_18IFBAM-1 to 4	Du_Ref case with 18 IFBA MAs mixed with WgPuO_2 (1) 5 wt.%, (2) 10 wt.%, (3) 15 wt.%, and (4) 20 wt.%.
Du_30IFBAM-1 to 4	Du_Ref case with 30 IFBA MAs mixed with WgPuO_2 (1) 5 wt.%, (2) 10 wt.%, (3) 15 wt.%, and (4) 20 wt.%.

Results and discussions

In the current analysis, calculations were conducted with the absence of soluble boron in the moderator (0 ppm), and all control rods were fully withdrawn. The simulations were carried out at the temperatures outlined in Table 3, maintaining a constant power density of 40 kW/kg for all cases. It's noteworthy that in these neutronic calculations, the outer surfaces of the assemblies were treated as reflective, indicating the absence of neutron leakage and the eigenvalues will be considered infinite multiplication factor (k_{inf}). However, in a typical large pressurized water reactor, such as a VVER, there's usually about a 3% neutron leakage rate (as reported by Hernandez and Brown 2020). Therefore, in this context, the term "criticality period" refers to the burnup period during which k_{inf} reaches 1.03 (as denoted by the dashed lines in the figures).

Multiplication factors and criticality periods

$\text{WgPuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ duplex vs. LEU fuel

A comparison to the LEU fuel is required to investigate the performance of neutronic behavior, discharge burnup, and fuel cycle of the $\text{WgPuO}_2\text{-ThO}_2$ duplex fuel when it is incorporated into the VVER assembly. The multiplication factor serves as the fundamental value to evaluate the behavior of these parameters. Fig. 6 depicts the k_{inf} values of LEU (LEU-Ref) and the duplex fuel design under consideration (Du-Ref) versus burnup. The reactivity of the

Du-Ref at the BOC is less than that of LEU-Ref because of the larger thermal neutron absorption cross-section of Th-232 than U-238. Even so, the reactivity of the Du-Ref decreases more slowly with burnup than the reactivity of LEU-Ref due to the formation of fissile U-233, Pu-239 and Pu-241. At the end of the LEU irradiation, the reactivity of the Du-Ref case is still higher than that of LEU-Ref. This implies that the considered duplex fuel has sufficient reactivity to burn for a longer period of time, which gives the duplex fuel an advantage in longer fuel cycle schemes. In terms of criticality periods, the Du-Ref case attains the criticality period at 84.92 GWd/ton, which is equivalent to 5.81 equivalent full power years (EFPYs). The LEU-Ref case, on the other hand, only achieves the criticality period at 36.12 GWd/ton, which corresponds to 2.47 EFPYs.

Effects of MAs addition on Du-Ref

Next step is to look into the MAs cases trend of k_{inf} with the reference duplex model. Fig. 7 depicts the results as a function of burnup, where (a) represents the coated cases and (b) represents the mixed cases. Since MA nuclides have large thermal neutron capture cross-sections, the k_{inf} values at BOC will certainly decrease as the quantity of MAs in the fuel increases along with the displacement of fissile material. Furthermore, the reactivity suppression followed the same trend for both configurations (i.e. coated and mixed), and the suppression increased with the increase of the IFBAs in the assembly. However, as evident in Fig. 8, the decrease rate ($|\Delta k|$) determined by equation (1) was higher in all coated cases, resulting in a margin-

ally significant reactivity suppression when compared to their corresponding values in mixed cases, more precisely, 25% higher on average for all cases. This entire scenario is due to differences in the degree of self-shielding in terms of MAs design and placement, whether homogeneous or heterogeneous. The distribution of MAs over a larger area reduces the self-shielding effect (Evans et al. 2022). As a result, the reactivity suppression in mixed configurations is slightly lower than in coated configurations.

In terms of the criticality period (cycle length), it follows the same pattern as reactivity suppression, decreasing as the number of MAs and IFBAs in the assembly increases. Yet, another difference between cycle lengths in both configurations is that the cycle length penalty in coated cases is about 1.08% on average, whereas the cycle length penalty in mixed cases is about 1.27% on average. Fig. 9 deficit the criticality periods for the considered cases.

Figure 6. Comparison of k_{inf} evolution vs. burnup (top), and accumulated burnup over EFPYs (bottom) for reference and duplex assemblies.

Figure 7. k_{inf} versus fuel burnup for a. Coated cases, and b. Mixed cases.

Figure 8. $|\Delta k|$, comparison between different loading designs a. Coated cases, and b. Mixed cases.

Figure 9. Criticality periods, comparison between different loading designs a. Coated cases, and b. Mixed cases.

$$|\Delta k| = \left| \frac{k_i}{k_{Du_Ref}} - 1 \right| \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Where k_i is the calculated multiplication factor at BOC after adding MAS, and k_{Du_Ref} is the multiplication factor for the WgPuO₂-ThO₂ duplex case multiplied by 100 to get results with %.

Isotopic concentrations change with burnup

Plutonium concentrations

Fig. 10 illustrates the plutonium isotopic concentrations at BOC and EOC (end of the cycle) for all MAS cases at the same irradiation period. As the Du_Ref case without initial MAS, this case serves as an initial point for further comparison with the other cases.

The only isotope of plutonium that exhibits depletion during the simulation is Pu-239 which positively impacts the total depleted plutonium concentrations (Fig. 11). More precisely, the depletion value for Pu-239 in Du_Ref is approximately 88.81% from its initial concentration, and the rate increases as the amount of MAS increases, from 0.02% to 0.32% for coated cases and 0.04% to 0.39% for mixed cases. In terms of Pu-239 weight percent at discharged fuels, Pu-239 in Du_Ref case accounts for approximately 31.74 wt.%, and the addition of MAS reduces this value by 0.13% to 1.38% for coated cases and 0.15% to 1.50% for mixed cases. Otherwise, employing WgPuO₂-ThO₂ fuel increased the concentrations of Pu-238, Pu-240, Pu-241, and Pu-242 by 2002.40%, 143.14%, 1602.14%, and 6834.71%, respectively, throughout burnup. To represent approximately 1.27 wt.%, 42.66 wt.%, 18.03 wt.%, and 6.29 wt.%,

Figure 10. Assembly-averaged plutonium isotopic concentrations at BOC and EOC.

Figure 11. Assembly-averaged total plutonium concentrations at BOC and EOC.

respectively, at discharged fuel. The use of MAs increases the accumulation of Pu-238 at discharged fuel by 0.22 wt.% to 2.19 wt.% for coated cases and 0.22 wt.% to 2.20 wt.% for mixed cases, this is primarily due to increased production from Np-237 neutron captures. Pu-242 weight percent at discharged fuel increased by plus 0.01 wt.% to 0.14 wt.% for mixed cases and 0.02 wt.% to 0.15 wt.% for coated cases because Pu-242 is mainly formed from Am-241. Pu-240 and Pu-241 undertook, however, slightly decrease at discharge, by 0.07 wt.% to 0.71 wt.% coated cases and 0.07 wt.% to 0.70 wt.% for mixed cases for Pu-240, and 0.03 wt.% to 0.25 wt.% coated cases and 0.02 wt.% to 0.12 wt.% for mixed cases for Pu-241. Overall, comparing the presented results reveals that the difference between homogeneous and heterogeneous loadings was relatively small.

MAs isotopes

The behavior of the analyzed MA isotopes, considered in this study, is shown in Fig. 12. As presented in the graphic representation, only Np-237 concentrations decrease with burnup, whereas Am-241, Am-243, Cm-244, and Cm-245 concentrations accumulate with burnup. Np-237 concentration decreased by 58.30% to 69.58% in coated cases and 58.26% to 69.12% in mixed cases, as a result of its transmutation. The successful transmutations of Np-237 reduce the stockpile because it is the main constituent of the MAs in depleted nuclear fuel. Am-241 accumulation, on the other hand, exhibits very interesting behavior in that its accumulation rate decreases as initial concentration increases, for example, in coated cases the accumulation rate falls from 974.20% to 7.17%, and in mixed cases the accumulation rate falls from 988.59% to 11.89%, from its concentration at BOC. What's more, when compared to the Du_Ref case, Am-241 concentration at EOC decreased by 0.05% to 0.29% for coated cases and increased by 0.33% to 3.28% for mixed cases, which means that using Am-241 in a coated configuration (heterogeneous) enhance its transmutation. The accumulation rate of the remaining MAs, Am-243, Cm-244, and Cm-245, decreased as initial concentrations increased, similar to Am-241. For Am-243, the accumulation rate decreases from 2369.29% to 164.57% in coated cases and from 2395.28% to 169.51% in mixed cases. For Cm-244, the accumulation rate decreases from 3626.10%

to 461.42% in coated cases and from 3600.71% to 423.30% in mixed cases. In the case of Cm-245, the accumulation rate decreases from 8802.17% to 1096.58% in coated cases and from 9244.68% to 1343.07% in mixed cases, from their concentrations at BOC. Unfortunately, at the discharge, their concentrations were higher than those produced by the Du_Ref. Am-243 concentration increased by 0.64% to 7.82% in coated cases and by 0.74% to 8.97% in mixed cases. Cm-244 concentration increased by 6.07% to 59.82% in coated cases and by 4.36% to 47.79% in mixed cases. Cm-245 concentration increased by 4.08% to 39.89% in coated cases and by 8.22% to 67.38% in mixed cases. Besides coated cases produce less Am-243 and Cm-245, but more Cm-244. Based on the results of the simulation calculations, it is strongly advised that future research should focus on the incorporation of enriched minor actinides, specifically NpO₂ or AmO₂. These particular actinides constitute the majority of the total minor actinides found in depleted LWR fuel and display promising transmutation rates.

Th-232 and U-233 concentrations

One of the primary goals of using thorium-based fuel is to produce U-233, a valuable fissile material for future use (Colton and Bromley 2018). This is due primarily to the advantageous properties of Th-232, which has a thermal neutron absorption cross-section roughly three times that of U-238. Within the thermal neutron spectrum, this property results in a significantly higher rate of transmutation into fissile U-233. Furthermore, when compared to U-235 and Pu-239, U-233 has the highest neutron reproduction factor. As a result, U-233 has the potential to become a valuable future energy resource, improving the resilience and sustainability of the nuclear fuel cycle while reducing proliferation risks.

The concentrations of Th-232 and U-233 at BOC and EOC for all examined cases are illustrated in Fig. 13. As explained previously in the MAs incorporation design section, MAs loading only directly impacts the WgPuO₂ zone in the duplex cases, resulting in the same initial Th-232 concentration for all cases. The addition of MAs, however, increases U-233 breeding by 0.01% to 0.06% (steadily increasing as MAs loading increases) due to a decrease in fissile Pu-239, which has a high ability to absorb thermal neutrons.

Figure 12. Assembly-averaged MA concentrations at BOC and EOC.

Safety parameters analysis

This section evaluates the safety parameters, particularly the feedback coefficients, of LEU, duplex, and duplex fuels with the considered MAs loading at BOC. They were evaluated to improve the understanding of reactivity changes caused by various phenomena that can occur in the considered assembly. Generally, there is a requirement that these coefficients must be negative when an LWR is in a critical state (Fejt et al. 2019). As a result, the main following feedback effects are examined:

- Fuel temperature coefficient (FTC): fuel temperature increased from 1100 K to 1200 K.
- Moderator temperature coefficient (MTC): moderator temperature increased from 573 K to 600 K (density 0.6549 g/cm³).
- Boron worth coefficient (BWC): boron concentration in the moderator increased from 0 to 400 ppm.

Reactivity feedback coefficients are determined by using equation (2) (El Banni et al. 2022), and the resulting coefficients are presented in Table 8.

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{X_2 - X_1} \left(\frac{k_2 - k_1}{k_2 \cdot k_1} \right) \cdot 10^5 \quad (2)$$

where α is the evaluated coefficient (i.e. FTC, MTC, or BWC), X_1 and X_2 are the changes the considered parameters, k_1 and k_2 are the multiplication factors resulting from states X_1 and X_2 respectively, multiplied by 10⁵ to obtain results in pcm.

The first thing that stands out from a safety perspective is that the FTC of the duplex-based fuel is higher than that of the LEU model. This is due to the Doppler effect of Th-232. Further, when incorporating MAs and increasing their quantity, the resonance capture of thermal neutrons will be enhanced accordingly. Meanwhile, as fuel temperature increases, the negative value of FTC rises

Figure 13. Assembly-averaged Th-232 and U-233 concentrations at BOC and EOC.

due to Doppler broadening from MAs captures as well. Moreover, by incorporating more MAs into the considered WgPuO₂-ThO₂ duplex fuel, the negative reactivity changes caused by MAs captures can improve the less negative MTC caused by the slightly shifted Maxwellian region of Pu-239 neutron spectrum, which improves its fission resonances. Similarly, the incorporation of MAs improves the magnitude (less negative) of BWC for the reference duplex fuel since boron is a thermal neutron absorber, and plutonium-based fuels may exhibit significantly reduced thermal neutron fluxes (Carbajo 2005). Higher MAs incorporation patterns can thus be used to partially substitute or reduce the boron concentration in the moderator because MTCs will be much less negative at higher concentrations.

Table 8. Feedback coefficients for the examined cases

Case Name	FTC [pcm/K]	MTC [pcm/K]	BWC [pcm/ppm]
LEU_Ref	-1.599	-36.954	-4.920
Du_Ref	-2.014	-20.255	-3.526
Du_12IFBAC-1	-2.019	-20.613	-3.538
Du_12IFBAC-2	-2.025	-20.822	-3.547
Du_12IFBAC-3	-2.031	-20.995	-3.556
Du_12IFBAC-4	-2.038	-21.149	-3.566
Du_18IFBAC-1	-2.022	-20.712	-3.545
Du_18IFBAC-2	-2.031	-21.022	-3.559
Du_18IFBAC-3	-2.040	-21.287	-3.573
Du_18IFBAC-4	-2.049	-21.519	-3.587
Du_30IFBAC-1	-2.027	-20.965	-3.554
Du_30IFBAC-2	-2.042	-21.467	-3.578
Du_30IFBAC-3	-2.058	-21.905	-3.602
Du_30IFBAC-4	-2.074	-22.294	-3.625
Du_12IFBAM-1	-2.015	-20.638	-3.533
Du_12IFBAM-2	-2.017	-20.876	-3.539
Du_12IFBAM-3	-2.021	-21.091	-3.546
Du_12IFBAM-4	-2.025	-21.276	-3.552
Du_18IFBAM-1	-2.015	-20.771	-3.537
Du_18IFBAM-2	-2.019	-21.123	-3.546
Du_18IFBAM-3	-2.024	-21.438	-3.556
Du_18IFBAM-4	-2.030	-21.712	-3.566
Du_30IFBAM-1	-2.017	-21.045	-3.543
Du_30IFBAM-2	-2.024	-21.623	-3.559
Du_30IFBAM-3	-2.033	-22.140	-3.575
Du_30IFBAM-4	-2.042	-22.598	-3.591

Concluding remarks and suggestions for future works

This study compares the neutronic performance of an LEU fuel and an innovative PuO₂-ThO₂ duplex-based fuel in a VVER-1200 assembly using the DRAGON lattice physics code yielded valuable insights. In this duplex configuration, WgPuO₂ (enriched in Pu-239) was used in the inner perimeter, while pure ThO₂ was used in the outer perimeter, effectively recycling excess Pu-239 and producing U-233. One noteworthy finding was the remarkable increase in burnup, up to 135%, achieved by the duplex fuel when compared to an LEU fuel with an equivalent constant power density. Additionally, the duplex fuel exhibited a reduced reactivity swing throughout the fuel cycle, which is a crucial safety consideration.

The use of MAs to mitigate excess reactivity was also examined, with two MA configurations investigated: one involving coated MAs and the other involving MAs mixed with the WgPuO₂ fuel. Notably, coating MAs with WgPuO₂ fuel resulted in slightly higher reactivity suppression at BOC and a slightly lower burnup penalty when compared to mixing MAs with WgPuO₂ fuel. The study also scrutinized the isotopic composition of the discharged fuel. The use of MAs resulted in significant Pu-239 transmutation, lowering even-numbered plutonium isotopes and increasing resistance to proliferation. However, it also resulted in higher concentrations of Pu-238, Pu-242, Am-243, Cm-244, and Cm-245 in the discharged fuel. Importantly, the reactivity coefficients (FTC, MTC, and BWC) of the investigated cases were mainly negative, with FTC being noticeably more negative in MAs cases due to Doppler broadening from MAs captures. Higher MAs incorporation patterns can also be used to partially substitute or reduce the boron concentration in the moderator because MTCs will be much less negative at higher concentrations.

Future research could also focus on core designs will be explored, with a focus on further validating the feasibility of

the fuel and assembly arrangements to enhance the practicality of the duplex fuel. This will encompass investigations into safety parameters and variations in duplex configurations, such as ThO₂-WgPuO₂. Additionally, future research will extend to the examination of alternative burnable absorbers, it will also delve into coupled neutronic and thermal-hydraulic studies to gain a comprehensive understanding of the system's performance under various conditions.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Achraf Radi: Resources, Data curation, Investigation, Writing - original draft. Ouadie Kabach: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Supervision, Validation, Writing - review & editing. El Mahjoub Chakir: Supervision, Formal analysis, review & editing.

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Data availability statement

This paper and the references therein contain all the data to reproduce and validate the presented results.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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